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Title: THE FUTURE OF STORYTELLING with AI and VR

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INTRODUCTION:

Gathering data around viewership around video on demand platforms is not creating the affinity necessary to keep viewers hooked to television shows. Most shows are driven by BINGE or BANTER scenarios. And as more and more series, films are released on a daily, weekly, and monthly basis to find the right content for the right audience is getting harder and harder.

To make this more complicated, virtual reality and immersive content have not shown the promise as we were led to believe as most productions use immersive in the same way they would a two dimensional production.

But what if you could combine data gathering, audience affinity building and immersive in one integrated offering that disrupts all media, entertainment and advertising?

AIM:

Virtual Reality must make future filmmakers re-think how storytelling is done. And the same should be said for how consumers find films and media as search limits the available content and who it would attract. That's why artificial intelligence or better stated conversational commerce is the way forward to discovering your new favorite show.

And if the show is immersive, it gives insights to the real world on how a viewer really behaves.

KEYWORDS:

Virtual Reality, Immersive Analytics, Artificial Intelligence, Conversational Commerce, Media & Entertainment

BIOGRAPHY:

Jackson brings two decades of experiences in IT, Enterprise Architecture, Data Science, Big Data Engineering and Quantifiable Media with multinational companies around the world. He has lived in Hong Kong, Philippines, South Africa, Brasil, and Germany but originally from the United States.